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Research Article

**A DESCRIPTIVE RESEARCH TO ASSESS THE ONSET OF
HCV (HEPATITIS C VIRUS) ANTIBODIES RELEVANCE
AMONG COMMUNITY BARBERSOP VISITORS**¹Dr. Bilal Hassan, ²Dr Ahmad Mustafa, ²Dr. Shahid Muhammad¹House Officer, Jinnah Hospital, Lahore²Rular Health centre Tibbi Qaisrani, Taunsa Sharif, Dera Ghazi Khan**Abstract:**

Objective: Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) can potently transfer through underutilized shaving kits and blades when shared or used more than once by different users. We aimed to determine the HCV antibodies prevalence and reaction among hospitalized patients who were common visitors of roadside barbers.

Methodology: Our descriptive research completed in the timeframe of July 2016 to June 2017 at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore. We studied the demographic information of the patients which included the information about educational level, marital status, occupation and age. We also documented the per month visit frequency to roadside barbers, duration and associated clinical information from the patients. We included all those participants who were visiting roadside barbers for more than three months; whereas, we did not include any patient of liver disease history, dental surgery, blood transfusion, intravenous drug users, tattooing, regular injectable medicine users, hemodialysis cases and multiple sex partners in this research. During hospitalization, we took blood samples of all the patients and screened them for antibodies of HCV through ELISA Kit.

Results: Research sample consisted on one hundred and eighty-four male patients with a mean age of (33.8 ± 13.2) years. Among these patients, a number of patients were illiterate and belonged to a lower status. A total of 70 out of 184 patients (38%) were positive for HCV antibodies reactivity. Elder age group paid more visits to roadside barbers than younger age group especially under the age of forty years P-values (0.015 & 0.02). No significant association was reported among various marital status, education and socioeconomic groups in terms of HCV-antibodies reactivity prevalence.

Conclusion: In the light of research outcomes, we conclude that unsterilized shaving equipment and sharing of once used razors on multiple individuals is a potent source of HCV transmission from one person to another and it may also result in an onset of HCV. Multiple shaving exposures and prolonged duration may also increase the HCV transmission rate among roadside barber visitors.

Keywords: Antibodies, Hepatitis-C Virus (HCV), Roadside Barbers, Shaving Kits, Razors and Prevalence.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Bilal Hassan,**House Officer, Jinnah Hospital,
Lahore

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

The onset of HCV is commonly reported all over the world and Pakistan is also no exception to the onset of HCV as it is among serious problems of healthcare. Pakistan has no accurate epidemiological data on the incidence of HCV or it is very limited. According to the estimates of WHO, HCV is prevalent among three percent of the total world population with more than 170 million chronic HCV carriers all over the world [1]. There are various reports of HCV prevalence among various countries such as in Japan, USA, Europe and Pakistan with a respective infected estimated population of 2, 2.7, 5 and 10 million [2, 3]. Whereas, the Egyptian population is largely affected than any other country [4]. According to the definition of 1989, HCV is an RNA virus which is single-stranded and it belongs to Flavivirus virus family. Previously, HCV had an association with post-transfusion Hepatitis cases (90%) [5]. About 85% patient develop chronic HCV after an acute infection of HCV, Cirrhosis and Hepato-Cellular Carcinoma are respectively reported in 10% – 20% and 1% – 5% within a timeframe of 20 years – 30 years [5, 6].

HCV mostly transfers through blood transfusion, syringes reused, intravenous drug abuse, needles reused, multiple sexual partners, vertical transmission, ear piercing, inadequately sterilized dental and surgical instruments and tattooing [4, 7]. Among various other associated risk factors, the shaving of armpit and face shaving also attributes to the HCV transmission by community barber. Armpit and Face skin is delicate and it is also susceptible to an onset of microtrauma which leads to transfusion of HCV, which is more common with the use of contaminated razors of traditional long handle [8]. Regular visits to community barbers are also among the most prominent HCV transfusion causes all over Pakistan [9]. Therefore, we aimed to determine the HCV antibodies prevalence and reaction among hospitalized patients who were common visitors of roadside barbers.

METHODOLOGY:

Our descriptive research completed in the timeframe of July 2016 to June 2017 at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore. We studied the demographic information of the patients which included the information about educational level, marital status, occupation and age. We also documented the per month visit frequency to roadside barbers, duration

and associated clinical information from the patients. We included all those participants who were visiting roadside barbers for more than three months; whereas, we did not include any patient of liver disease history, dental surgery, blood transfusion, intravenous drug users, tattooing, regular injectable medicine users, hemodialysis cases and multiple sex partners in this research. During hospitalization, we took blood samples of all the patients and screened them for antibodies of HCV through ELISA Kit.

HCV IgG antibodies cut off value was more than 0.595, which was also taken as significant. On the requirement basis, other clinical assessments were also taken into consideration in the light of primary extended therapeutic interventions. Patients also followed regular follow-up after HCV antibodies positive identification and continued regular HCV treatment. The researcher analyzed the research outcomes on SPSS software (P-Value < 0.05).

RESULTS:

The research sample consisted on one hundred and eighty-four male patients with a mean age of (33.8 ± 13.2) years. Among these patients, a number of patients were illiterate and belonged to a lower status. A total of 70 out of 184 patients (38%) were positive for HCV antibodies reactivity. Elder age group paid more visits to roadside barbers than younger age group especially under the age of forty years P-values (0.015 & 0.02). No significant association was reported among various marital status, education and socioeconomic groups in terms of HCV-antibodies reactivity prevalence.

In terms of age and marital status 130 patients were under forty years of age; whereas, 111 were married. Various occupations had a different contribution in research samples such as labourers, farmers, shopkeepers, students, guards and others with respective proportions of 41.8%, 11.4%, 10.3%, 9.2%, 8.2% and 23.8%. The educational level of patients was illiterate, primary, middle, secondary, higher secondary and graduate with their respective proportions of 50.5%, 8.2%, 13.6%, 21.7%, 4.3% and 1.6%. In terms of visit timeframe there were 5 – 20 years, 21 – 40 years and under 5 years with respective proportions of 42.9%, 34.2% and 22.8%; whereas, per month frequency was 5 – 10 times, under 5 times and above 10 times having respective proportions of 84.3%, 12.8% and 3.8%. Detailed outcomes analysis is available in Table – I, II and III.

Table – I: Variables Stratification

Variables		Number	Percentage
Age and Marital Status	< 40 Years	130	71
	Married	111	60.3
Occupation	Labourers	77	41.8
	Farmers	21	11.4
	Shopkeepers	19	10.3
	Students	17	9.2
	Guards	15	8.2
	Others	45	23.8
Education	Illiterate	93	50.5
	Primary	15	8.2
	Middle	25	13.6
	Secondary	40	21.7
	Higher Secondary	8	4.3
Timeframe of Roadside Barber Visit	Graduate	3	1.6
	5 – 20 Years	79	42.9
	21 – 40 Years	63	34.2
Visit Frequency Per Month	Under 5 Years	42	22.8
	5 – 10 Times	154	84.3
	Under 5 Times	23	12.8
	Above 10 Times	7	3.8

Table – II: HCV Positive and HCV Negative with respect to Age Factor

Age	HCV Positive	HCV Negative
Age Above Forty Years	32	32
Age Under Forty Years	38	82

Table – III: HCV Positive and HCV Negative with respect to Shaving Years

Shaving Years	HCV Positive	HCV Negative
Under Twenty	40	83
Above Twenty	30	31

DISCUSSION:

All those visiting roadside barbers clearly show a prevalence of HCV among patients. HCV prevalence is mostly reported among various regions of the world [10]. The range of the HCV-antibodies prevalence among various countries such as USA, Africa, India and Pakistan is respectively 1.8%, 5.2%, 4.8% and 6% respectively with an overall world population in the range of (0.30% – 0.07%); whereas, highest reported rate of 22% in Egyptian population [4, 6, 11 – 14].

A rapid increase of HCV is visible among Pakistani population since 1994 as reported by Agbotwalla, Kakepotot and Nafees [10, 15, 16]. About ten million people are estimated to be HCV positive in Pakistan because of barber shops, intravenous drug users, blood donors and routine blood transfusion [3]. Higher rates of HCV-antibodies are also reported by Bhutta and Anwar with respective proportions of 66.75 & 46% among community barber visitors [17, 18].

Various authors also suggest that an unnecessary use

of injections, blood transfusion and unsterilized needles are potent HCV transmission sources in our country [3, 19, 20]. Hemodialysis also causes 23.7% to 68% HCV-antibodies prevalence [21]. No pet reports are available about the incidence of blood transfusion causing HCV infection among the Pakistani population [9]. Higher HCV prevalence is higher in the age group of 40 years to 50 years which is the same as our research outcomes [22]. Increasing age is at continuous risk because of increased exposure to HCV contributing factors [13].

Increased duration of visiting roadside barbers causes more chances of HCV-antibodies prevalence as the individuals are more prone to risk factors. There was no significant variation among bachelor and married population which is same as reported by various other authors [23]. There is a negligible HCV transmission among the monogamous couple, especially in case of negative HCV PCR [24]. Same has been reported in our research outcomes [24]. There is a valid need for improving better preventive healthcare practices among the general population in order to avoid the HCV infection.

CONCLUSION:

In the light of research outcomes, we conclude that unsterilized shaving equipment and sharing of once used razors on multiple individuals is a potent source of HCV transmission from one person to another and it may also result in an onset of HCV. Multiple shaving exposures and prolonged duration may also increase the HCV transmission rate among roadside barber visitors.

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